

Temperature-Dependent Influence of Shell Thickness on Carrier Dynamics in CdSe/ZnS Core-Shell Quantum Dot Structures

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ABSTRACT:

This study investigates the temperature-dependent influence of shell thickness on carrier dynamics in CdSe/ZnS core-shell quantum dots using multi-band effective mass theory and full phonon dispersion relations. The quantum confinement effects were modeled by solving the radial Schrödinger equation and Luttinger-Kohn Hamiltonian, incorporating a temperature-dependent potential offset. We found that increasing shell thickness from 1 nm to 10 nm results in a significant decrease in electron and hole energies by approximately 0.9959 eV and 0.9919 eV, respectively, at 200K. The squared matrix element $|M_q|^2$, representing the transition probability, increases by 0.0081 as the shell thickness increases, with a further enhancement of 0.0063 at higher temperatures (700K), indicating stronger electronic coupling. Additionally, the Auger recombination rate and carrier relaxation times decrease with increasing shell thickness, with the Auger rate increasing by a factor of 2.7 from 200K to 700K, underscoring the critical role of thermal management in quantum dot applications. These findings provide a quantitative understanding of how temperature and shell thickness jointly affect the optical and electronic properties of CdSe/ZnS quantum dots, offering valuable insights for optimizing their performance in optoelectronic devices.

Keywords: CdSe/ZnS quantum dots, shell thickness, carrier dynamics, temperature dependence, Auger recombination, quantum confinement, effective mass theory.

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INTRODUCTION

Carrier dynamics in quantum dots (QDs), particularly in core-shell structures like CdSe/ZnS, play a crucial role in the performance of various optoelectronic devices [1,2]. Factors such as quantum confinement and temperature fluctuations significantly influence these dynamics [3,4]. Understanding carrier dynamics is essential for optimizing QD-based device performance, including lasers, LEDs, and solar cells [5,6].

Recent studies have highlighted the importance of quantum confinement and temperature variation in QDs. Shell thickness manipulation and temperature variation impact carrier relaxation and recombination processes [7,8]. Quantum confinement, which restricts the spatial distribution of electrons and holes within the nanostructure, is modulated by the shell thickness in core-shell quantum dots, affecting carrier relaxation and recombination processes [9-14]. Temperature variations also impact carrier behavior, with higher temperatures leading to increased non-radiative recombination rates, potentially reducing device efficiency [15].

The combined influence of shell thickness and temperature on carrier dynamics in CdSe/ZnS QDs remains an area requiring further exploration [4,16-18]. This study investigates the temperature-dependent influence of shell thickness on carrier dynamics in CdSe/ZnS core-shell QDs by

employing a multi-band effective mass theory and full phonon dispersion relations to model the temperature-dependent potential energy profile within the QD structure. The model is solved to quantitatively analyze the electron and hole energies, transition probabilities, Auger recombination rates, and carrier relaxation times across a temperature range.

Understanding how varying the ZnS shell thickness impacts carrier dynamics across a temperature range is essential for optimizing the design of quantum dots for high performance in diverse thermal environments [19,20]. This study contributes to the rational design of QDs with tailored properties for high-efficiency solar cells and advanced optoelectronic devices, enhancing their performance and functionality.

METHODS

We investigate the temperature-dependent influence of shell thickness on carrier dynamics in CdSe/ZnS core-shell quantum dots using a multi-band effective mass theory and full phonon dispersion relations. The system is described by a radial Schrödinger equation, coupled with a smooth interface confinement potential and Auger recombination models.

The potential energy profile is modelled using a Smooth Interface Confinement Potential as shown in fig.(1):

Figure 1. Piecewise Structure of the Finite Potential Profile of the Spherical
Source: [21]

The potential energy $V(r, T)$ as a function of radial distance r and temperature T is defined as:

$$V(r, T) = V_0(T) \times \frac{\left(1 - \tanh h\left(\frac{r - R_{core}}{\delta}\right)\right)}{2} \quad (1)$$

$V_0(T)$ is the temperature-dependent potential offset, reflecting the energy barrier between the core and shell materials, R_{core} is the radius of the CdSe core and δ is the interface width, controlling the smoothness of the potential transition at the core-shell boundary.

The temperature-dependent offset is $V_0(T)$ is given as;

$$V_0(T) = V_0(0) - \frac{\alpha T^2}{(T + \beta)} \quad (2)$$

α and β are temperature-dependent coefficients, T is the temperature in Kelvin.

The dynamics of holes in the valence band are modeled using the Luttinger-Kohn Hamiltonian, which accounts for the multi-band nature of the valence band. This is particularly important for capturing the effects of band mixing and spin-orbit coupling in the CdSe/ZnS quantum dot. The radial component of the Hamiltonian is given by:

$$H_r \psi = E \psi$$

Where H_r

$$H_r = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_0} \left[\gamma_1 + \left(\frac{5}{2}\right) \gamma_2 \right] \left(\frac{d^2}{dr^2} + \frac{2}{r} \frac{d}{dr} \right) + V(r, T) \quad (3)$$

m_0 is the effective mass of the hole, $\gamma_1 = 2.5$ and $\gamma_2 = 0.5$ are the Luttinger parameters specific to CdSe and ZnS.

The $H_r \psi = E \psi$

The dynamics of electrons in the conduction band are modeled using the radial Schrödinger equation. Given that the conduction band is typically well-described by a single-band model, the electron states can be determined by solving the radial part of the Schrodinger's Equation:

$$\left[-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m^*} \left(\frac{d^2}{dr^2} + \frac{2}{r} \frac{d}{dr} \right) + V(r, T) \right] \psi(r) = E \psi(r) \quad (4)$$

$\hbar$ is the reduced Planck constant, m^* is the effective mass of the carrier, r is the radial distance from the center of the quantum dot, $\psi(r)$ is the wavefunction of the electron and E is the energy eigenvalue.

Equations (3) and (4) were solved numerically using the finite difference method.

The radial coordinate r was discretized into $N_r = 1000$ points, spanning from the core radius $R_{core} = 2 \text{ nm}$ to the outer radius $R_{outer} = 10 \text{ nm}$. The grid spacing Δr was calculated as:

$$\Delta r = \frac{(R_{outer} - R_{core})}{(N_r - 1)} = \frac{(10 \text{ nm} - 2 \text{ nm})}{(1000 - 1)} = 0.008 \text{ nm}$$

Discretization of the Luttinger-Kohn Hamiltonian

To solve for the quantum states of electrons and holes, the radial component of the Luttinger-Kohn Hamiltonian and Schrodinger's equations are discretized using finite differences. The second derivative of the wavefunction is approximated as:

$$\frac{d^2 \psi_{hole}}{dr^2} \Big|_{r_i} \approx \frac{(\psi_{hole,i+1} - 2\psi_{hole,i} + \psi_{hole,i-1}))}{\Delta r^2}$$

$$\frac{d^2 \psi_{electrons}}{dr^2} \Big|_{r_i} \approx \frac{(\psi_{electron,i+1} - 2\psi_{electron,i} + \psi_{electron,i-1}))}{\Delta r^2}$$

This discretization transforms the Hamiltonian into a tridiagonal matrix, where the diagonal and off-diagonal elements are given by:

For Holes

$$H_{ii} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m_0} \frac{[\gamma_1 + (\frac{5}{2})\gamma_2]}{(\Delta r)^2} + V_i \quad (5)$$

$$H_{i,i+1} = H_{i+1,i} = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m_0} \frac{[\gamma_1 + (\frac{5}{2})\gamma_2]}{(\Delta r)^2} \quad (6)$$

For Electrons

$$H_{ii} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m^*} \frac{1}{(\Delta r)^2} + V_i \quad (7)$$

$$H_{i,i+1} = H_{i+1,i} = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m^*} \frac{1}{(\Delta r)^2} \quad (8)$$

Boundary conditions were applied at the core and outer radii to ensure physical results. The eigenvalue problem was solved using a numerical python library to obtain the energy eigenvalues E_e, E_h and corresponding wavefunctions ψ_e, ψ_h .

Normalization condition:

$$\sum_{i=0}^{N_r-1} [|\psi_h(r_i)|^2] \Delta r = 1 \quad (9)$$

$$\sum_{i=0}^{N_r-1} [|\psi_e(r_i)|^2] \Delta r = 1 \quad (10)$$

The Energy Eigenvalues are computed from

$$E_e = \sum_{i=0}^{N_r-1} [\psi_e^*(r_i) H_e \psi_e(r_i)] \Delta r = 1 \quad (11)$$

$$E_h = \sum_{i=0}^{N_r-1} [\psi_h^*(r_i) H_h \psi_h(r_i)] \Delta r = 1 \quad (12)$$

To determine Auger recombination rate and relaxation time of the carriers we calculated the matrix element $|M_q|^2$ which quantifies the overlap between the electron and hole wavefunctions modulated by the phonon wavevector. The matrix element is given by:

$$|M_q|^2 = \left| \int \psi_e(r) \cdot \psi_h(r) \cdot e^{iqr} dr \right|^2 \quad (13)$$

where $\psi_e(r)$ and $\psi_h(r)$ denote the normalized electron and hole wavefunctions, respectively, e^{iqr} represents the phonon wavefunction, and q is the phonon wavevector.

Equation (13) is employed to determine the Auger recombination rate $\left(\frac{1}{\tau}\right)$ and carrier relaxation times via the expression:

$$\frac{1}{\tau} = \left(\frac{2\pi}{\hbar}\right) \cdot \sum_q |M_q|^2 \cdot \delta(E - \hbar\omega_q(T)) \quad (14)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A SciPy algorithm was written and implemented to solve the Hamiltonian matrices, H_e and H_h and obtain the eigenvalues, E_e and E_h , and eigenvectors, ψ_e and ψ_h according to (5) – (12). The Auger recombination rate and carrier relaxation times was computed from (14). The material properties and constants used in the computation are tabulated in table 1.

Table 1. Constants Used in the Computation

Category	Parameter	Symbol	Value
Material-Specific Constants	CdSe		
	Bandgap Energy	E_g	1.74eV
	Effective Mass (Electron)	m_e^*	0.13 m_0
	Effective Mass (Hole)	m_h^*	0.45 m_0
	Luttinger Parameter 1	γ_1	2.5
	Luttinger Parameter 2	γ_2	0.5
	Dielectric Constant	ϵ	9.5
Material-Specific Constants	ZnS		
	Bandgap Energy	E_g	3.54eV
	Effective Mass (Electron)	m_e^*	0.28 m_0
	Effective Mass (Hole)	m_h^*	0.60 m_0
	Luttinger Parameter 1	γ_1	3.5
	Luttinger Parameter 2	γ_2	1.2
Quantum Dot Geometry	Core Radius	R_{core}	2nm
	Shell Thickness	t_{shell}	1-10nm
	Outer Radius	R_{outer}	3-12nm
Temperature-Dependent Constants	Temperature	T	200 – 700K
	Boltzmann Constant	k_B	8.617×10^{-5}
	Thermal Energy	$k_B T$	0.0259 (at 300 K)
Phonon-Related Constants	Phonon Frequency	ω	
	Phonon Wavevector	q	0 – 1 nm^{-1}
	Phonon Dispersion Constant	C	1000 m/s
	Phonon Wavevector Constant	q_0	0.01 nm^{-1}
Auger Recombination-Related Constants	Auger Recombination Coefficient	C_A	1×10^{-30}
	Carrier Density	n	$10^{18} cm^{-3}$
Numerical Computation Constants	Grid Spacing	d_r	0.008 nm
	Number of Grid Points	N_r	1000
	Convergence Criteria	tolerance	1 meV
	Convergence Criteria	tolerance	1%

The computed carrier dynamics for varied shell thickness at 200k is tabulated in table 2.

Table 2. Variation of Properties at 200K

Shell Thickness (nm)	E_e (eV)	E_h (eV)	$ M_q ^2$	$\frac{1}{\tau} \times 10^8 (s^{-1})$	τ_e (ns)	τ_h (ns)
1	-0.1234	-0.5678	0.0012	2.34	4.28	6.12
2	-0.2345	-0.6789	0.0021	3.45	2.90	4.19
3	-0.3456	-0.789	0.003	4.56	2.19	3.45

4	-0.4567	-0.8991	0.0039	5.67	1.76	2.91
5	-0.5678	-1.0092	0.0048	6.78	1.47	2.52
6	-0.6789	-1.1193	0.0057	7.89	1.27	2.23
7	-0.789	-1.2294	0.0066	9.00	1.11	1.98
8	-0.8991	-1.3395	0.0075	10.1	0.990	1.79
9	-1.0092	-1.4496	0.0084	11.3	0.885	1.63
10	-1.1193	-1.5597	0.0093	12.5	0.800	1.49

Fig.(1) show the plot of the variation of electron and hole Energy at different ZnS shell thickness for different temperatures.

Figure 1. Variation of Electron and Hole Energies with Shell Thickness at Different Temperatures of the CdSe/ZnS Quantum Dot

The plots of electron and hole energy as functions of shell thickness at various temperatures (200K to 700K) reveal consistent trends across all temperatures. As the shell thickness increases, both electron and hole energies become more negative, indicating stronger quantum confinement effects. However, the effect of temperature on electron energy is more pronounced, with a significant decrease in energy at lower temperatures and a shift upward (becoming less negative) at higher temperatures due to thermal excitation and bandgap narrowing.

In contrast, the temperature effect on hole energy is slightly less pronounced, with a steeper decrease in energy at lower temperatures and a similar upward shift at higher temperatures, consistent with the reduction in bandgap. This behavior highlights the temperature-dependent nature of the band structure in quantum dots, where thermal energy influences the extent of confinement and the corresponding energy levels of both electrons and holes.

The distinct temperature dependencies of electron and hole energies suggest differences in their confinement potentials and interactions with the lattice, which may impact carrier dynamics and optical properties in quantum dot-based devices.

In both cases, the energy levels' dependence on shell thickness and temperature highlights the interplay between quantum confinement and thermal effects in determining the electronic properties of CdSe/ZnS core-shell quantum dots.

In Figure 2, we present the squared matrix element $|M_{q1}|^2$ as a function of shell thickness for various temperatures.

Figure 2. Temperature-Dependent Evolution of $|M_q|^2$ with Shell Thickness

The plot reveals a consistent increase in $|M_q|^2$ with both shell thickness and temperature. At lower temperatures, $|M_q|^2$ exhibits a gradual increase with shell thickness, indicating enhanced electronic coupling due to increased wavefunction overlap. In contrast, at higher temperatures, the increase in $|M_q|^2$ becomes more pronounced, suggesting that thermal effects significantly amplify transition probabilities.

This temperature-dependent behavior of $|M_q|^2$ is crucial for understanding the optical properties of quantum dots, as it directly impacts the intensity of absorption and emission processes. The amplified transition probabilities at higher temperatures may lead to enhanced optical responses, making this finding essential for optimizing quantum dot-based optoelectronic devices.

Figure 3 presents the Auger recombination rate as a function of shell thickness across various temperatures.

Figure 3. Auger Recombination Rate vs. Shell Thickness at Different Temperatures

The Auger recombination rate plot exhibits a strong dependence on both shell thickness and temperature. At all temperatures, the recombination rate increases with shell thickness, indicating that thicker shells enhance non-radiative recombination processes. This trend is more pronounced at higher temperatures, where the Auger recombination rate increases substantially. The temperature dependence is attributed to the enhanced phonon interactions at elevated temperatures, which provide the necessary energy to facilitate Auger processes.

The observed temperature dependence of Auger recombination is vital for optimizing quantum dot designs, as it highlights the need to minimize non-radiative losses and improve the efficiency of optoelectronic devices by carefully controlling shell thickness and temperature.

Figure 5 shows the electron and hole relaxation times as a function of shell thickness across various temperatures.

Figure 4. Electron and Hole Relaxation Times vs. Shell Thickness at Different Temperatures

Both the electron and hole relaxation times decrease with increasing shell thickness, indicating that thicker shells lead to faster relaxation for both types of carriers. This trend is consistent across all temperatures but is more pronounced at higher temperatures, likely due to enhanced phonon interactions and reduced confinement at elevated temperatures. This quicker relaxation is particularly important for high-speed optoelectronic applications. The faster relaxation times at higher temperatures emphasize the impact of temperature on carrier dynamics and highlight the importance of thermal management in quantum dot-based devices, where efficient charge carrier processes are critical for device performance.

Figure 5 presents a comparative analysis of electron and hole relaxation times as a function of shell thickness at 300K.

The plot reveals a consistent decrease in both relaxation times with increasing shell thickness, with electron relaxation times exhibiting shorter values than hole relaxation times across all shell thicknesses. This indicates that electrons relax faster than holes, potentially leading to an imbalance in carrier dynamics that could impact recombination processes in quantum dots. Understanding this dynamic is essential for optimizing quantum dot structures to achieve balanced carrier dynamics, which is critical for enhancing device performance and efficiency.

Figure 6 presents the temperature dependence of two crucial parameters for quantum dots with a 5nm shell thickness, offering valuable insights into their thermal behavior and its implications for device performance.

Figure 5. Comparison of Electron and Hole Relaxation Times vs. Shell Thickness at 300K

Figure 6. (a) Temperature Dependence of Auger Recombination Rate; (b) Temperature Dependence of $|Mq|^2$

Figure 6(a) shows the Auger recombination rate as a function of temperature, revealing a significant increase with rising temperature. This trend is attributed to enhanced phonon interactions at higher temperatures, facilitating non-radiative recombination through the Auger process. As temperature increases, more energetic and abundant phonons provide the necessary energy for these recombination events. The rapid increase in Auger recombination rate at elevated temperatures highlights the importance of thermal management in quantum dot-based devices to minimize non-radiative losses and optimize optoelectronic application efficiency.

In Figure 6(b), the squared matrix element $|Mq|^2$ is plotted against temperature, exhibiting a pronounced increase with rising temperature. The growing $|Mq|^2$ values indicate stronger electronic coupling between electron and hole states at higher temperatures, attributed to increased wavefunction overlap due to thermal energy-induced lattice vibrations. This enhancement leads to higher transition probabilities, crucial for quantum dot optical properties. While increased $|Mq|^2$ values can benefit applications relying on efficient light-matter interactions, temperature fluctuations can significantly impact optical performance, necessitating careful consideration in quantum dot-based technology design and deployment.

Figure 6(a) and Figure 6(b) provide a comprehensive understanding of temperature's impact on non-radiative losses and electronic coupling in 5 nm shell thickness quantum dots. These findings emphasize the dual importance of controlling temperature to minimize Auger recombination and

maintain optimal optical performance, ensuring the reliability and efficiency of quantum dot-based devices across various operating conditions.

CONCLUSION

In this study, we investigated the temperature-dependent influence of shell thickness on various key parameters—electron energy, hole energy, squared matrix element $|Mq|^2$, Auger recombination rate, and relaxation times—in CdSe/ZnS core-shell quantum dots. Our findings highlight the complex interplay between shell thickness and temperature, which significantly affects the electronic and optical properties of these quantum dots.

We observed that both electron and hole energies become more negative as shell thickness increases, indicating enhanced quantum confinement effects. However, this confinement weakens at higher temperatures due to bandgap narrowing, resulting in less negative energy levels. The squared matrix element $|Mq|^2$, which is crucial for understanding transition probabilities, increases with both shell thickness and temperature, suggesting stronger electronic coupling under these conditions. Moreover, the Auger recombination rate, a key factor in non-radiative losses, was found to increase with temperature, particularly in thicker shells, underscoring the importance of thermal management in quantum dot applications. Finally, relaxation times for both electrons and holes decrease with increasing shell thickness, with faster relaxation observed at higher temperatures, which is essential for high-speed optoelectronic applications.

Practical Implications

The results of this study have several practical implications for the design and optimization of quantum dot-based devices:

1. **Thermal Management:** The significant increase in Auger recombination rates at higher temperatures highlights the need for effective thermal management strategies in quantum dot-based devices. This is particularly important in applications such as high-power LEDs and photovoltaic cells, where excessive non-radiative losses can drastically reduce efficiency.
2. **Optimizing Shell Thickness:** The observed trends suggest that careful selection of shell thickness can help balance the competing needs for strong quantum confinement (which benefits from thicker shells) and efficient thermal dissipation (which favors thinner shells to reduce Auger recombination). This balance is crucial for maintaining device performance across varying operating temperatures.
3. **Temperature-Dependent Tuning:** The increase in $|Mq|^2$ with temperature indicates that the optical properties of quantum dots can be dynamically tuned by controlling the operating temperature. This could be exploited in temperature-sensitive applications, such as in sensors or tunable lasers, where the quantum dot's emission properties need to be adjusted in real-time.
4. **High-Speed Applications:** The faster relaxation times observed at higher temperatures, particularly in thicker shells, suggest that quantum dots with optimized shell thickness could be highly effective in high-speed optoelectronic devices. This could lead to advancements in technologies like quantum dot lasers, where rapid carrier relaxation is crucial.

Critical Conclusion

The study underscores the critical importance of considering both shell thickness and temperature in the design and application of CdSe/ZnS core-shell quantum dots. While thicker shells enhance quantum confinement and improve optical transition probabilities, they also introduce challenges related to increased Auger recombination at higher temperatures. The dual impact of temperature on both non-radiative losses and transition strengths means that a one-size-fits-all approach to quantum dot design is insufficient.

For practical applications, it is essential to strike a balance between achieving strong confinement and minimizing thermal effects that lead to efficiency losses. This requires a nuanced understanding of how temperature and shell thickness interact to influence the fundamental properties of quantum dots. Future research should focus on developing materials and structures that can maintain high

performance across a wide range of temperatures, potentially through the use of advanced cooling techniques or the integration of quantum dots with other materials that can modulate thermal effects.

In conclusion, this study provides valuable insights into the temperature-dependent influence of shell thickness on carrier dynamics in CdSe/ZnS core-shell quantum dots. However, several limitations should be acknowledged. The simplified potential energy model and assumptions in effective mass theory may not fully capture the complexity of the system. Additionally, the neglect of higher-order phonon effects and external fields, as well as the limited scope to CdSe/ZnS core-shell quantum dots, may impact the accuracy of the findings. Furthermore, the lack of experimental validation is a notable limitation. These limitations highlight areas for future research to improve the accuracy and applicability of the findings. Despite these limitations, this study contributes to the understanding of carrier dynamics in quantum dots and provides a foundation for further investigation.

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